

Noise and Similarities between Coping Mechanisms for Autism, Comorbidities, and the Human Stress Response

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Autism is characterized by an inability to deal with variation or an inability to generalize in several areas of functioning. These can include an inability to understand the variations of the meaning of a word in context, difficulties dealing with changes in structure or schedule, and an inability to filter out unnecessary information in a stochastic environment. It has previously been theorized that this is similar to *overfitting* in mathematical models or the tendency to learn experiences too closely, focusing too much on the fine details of their learned experiences rather than the general “gist” of the experience.

In neural networks one of the main causes of overfitting is a lack of variation in training data. This can be combatted by artificially adding variation to said training data through adding noise to your data. Noise can be intuitively explained by thinking of an old-fashioned antenna-TV with not so great signal. You might not be able to see the fine details as well if there is static on the TV screen, but you can only get the general “gist” of what is going on. It has been found that children and adults with autism have low levels of exogenous neural noise (Davis & Plaisted-Grant 2015). In neural networks we can add layers of “noise” to add this variability to destroy un-necessary information and generalize better to a stochastic environment. Stanford neuroscientists have found that neural noise is key to learning (A. Adams 2015), and other questions have been raised that perhaps neural noise holds a function instead of just being a subpar encoding strategy (Nassar et. Al 2021).

In the presence of entropy, the fine details of each experience can only hurt us, so it would therefore be rational for the fine details of sensory information be destroyed. As stress and feelings of uncertainty of survival increase it seems that in several physiological reactions that additive sensory noise is present using all 5 senses as mentioned below.

Tingling

If you are experiencing tingling, and you viewed each second, moment, or nerve activation as a “frame” then each frame is going to be slightly different from each other creating additional variation to help generalize in response to uncertainty. This helps filter out unnecessary details and keep the general “gist” of the information. Tingling can be a symptom of several stress responses such as hypoglycemia, allergic reactions, and anxiety. Also the location of the tingling is also quite reasonable for this hypothesis with hypoglycemia and allergy because this tingling is commonly located around the mouth and hands, the parts of the body associated with eating.

Blurry Vision

Blurry vision can also be associated with hypoglycemia and stress responses. A part of how the brain processes visual information is through a process called edge detection which happens in the (V1) primary visual cortex (O’reilly et. Al). When noise is added via a “blur” to an image, it smooths the image and reduces the information to that of which is most important as shown below.

When it comes to differentiating between a cat and a dog, the edges associated with fur and the surrounding environment are mostly removed in the edges of the blurred image versus the edges of the original image. This is good because neither the fur or environment is particularly helpful to us in differentiating between a dog or a cat. Although a non-autistic brain does not view the world in a blurred form, it is likely because we have sufficient neural noise to filter this information in the neural pathways instead.

Tinnitus

Tinnitus can also be described as the addition of noise to sensory inputs, and is also a common part of human stress responses. Tinnitus is commonly associated with allergy, anxiety, and other stress responses. It is actually through this exact same process that movie effects associated with being “shellshocked” are created. (Blurring and ringing effect) By adding a similar frequency to tinnitus to audio datasets, classification problems can increase.

<input computational model for tinnitus>

Olfactory and Gustatory Hallucinations

Olfactory hallucinations A.K.A phantom smells as well as gustatory hallucinations are also associated with allergies and anxiety as well. This can be described as a layer of noise over olfactory and gustatory sensory inputs. While these senses are difficult to reproduce with a neural network, the trend of managing entropy with the destruction of information continues.

The Relativity of Entropy Management

A potential reason that non-autistic adults don't commonly walk around with noisy symptoms all the time, is because relative to the entropy in their environment they have sufficient neural noise. Sensory noise is only added in a compensatory manner in stressful scenarios, so sensory noise is only added with . However with an autistic adult with lowered neural noise, they are lacking neural noise in respect to that required by the entropy in their environment, this often involves a significantly reduced quality of life and a need to reduce the entropy of their environment by living in a controlled environment with a rigid routine. If this were to be true, then autistic adults

would theoretically be walking around with noisy symptoms and symptoms mimicking data augmentations all the time, and coping mechanisms similar to adding noise would be helpful as well.

Coping Mechanisms and Treatments

Fidget Stimming

By playing with sensory fidget toys, are autistic children and adults not just adding peripheral nervous stimulation in a similar way to the body causing peripheral nervous stimulation in hypoglycemia and allergy?

White Noise Machines

By playing white noise from a machine, or by playing Binaural beats are we not adding noise to aural sensory inputs? Noise is important in filtering, therefore it is predictive that a white noise machine should help an autistic individual manage aural sensory overload.

Head Tilting

A form of data augmentation, head tilting is common in children and adults alike when it comes to processing information. The increased head tilting seen in autistic individuals can be not only evidence of impaired information processing, but a compensatory measure to help generalize by adding another variation of visual information similar to how we train image classification networks by rotating photos.

Self Destructive Behavior

If autistic individuals are lacking noise in the information processing chain, whether it be neural or sensory noise, and stress responses increase noise in this information processing chain in a similar way to other coping mechanisms for autism, perhaps this relation between noise, its role in learning in stochastic environments, and the stress response could be descriptive in understanding the role of self destructive behavior as a compensatory behavior in the management of stochastic environments rather than just as a symptom.

Comorbidities

Quite a few comorbidities with autism are also versions of data augmentation or additive noise and instead of viewing these as symptoms I hypothesize that they are actually compensatory measures to help survival in stochastic environments with reduced neural noise.

Tinnitus

While normally present in 15-20% of the normal population, the prevalence of tinnitus in autism has a prevalence of up to 70%.

Peripheral Neuropathy

The prevalence of peripheral neuropathies is significantly increased in autism although the exact number is still being researched. In the general population 1-7% of individuals have been diagnosed with a peripheral neuropathy.

Visual Snow Syndrome

Very Similar to “Salt And Pepper Noise” visual snow syndrome is another way of adding noise to ocular sensory information. Visual snow syndrome is a fairly uncommon neurological condition effecting 2-3% of people worldwide. Autism spectrum disorder is a risk factor for developing visual snow syndrome, is this a coincidence that these “noisy” symptoms are predictive for being associated with autism?

Amblyopia (Lazy Eye)

The way that Amblyopia effects vision is by making your vision blurry. Instead of just being a “symptom” it is possible that Amblyopia is in fact a compensatory measure to assist in the filtering of ocular sensory information in the pretense of reduced neural noise. A sizable number of autistic patients have Amblyopia ranging from 19-31% of the population, where in the general population is around 2-4%.

Strabismus (Crossed Eyes)

Normally effecting only 2-4% of the population versus roughly 15% of autistic children and adults, crossed eyes can be viewed as a form of data augmentation. This might help explain why up to 15% of people with autism have this condition. The benefits of double vision on visual classification performance in entropic environments can be proven by augmenting each image with a transformation mimicking strabismus and then testing performance versus the original image.

Double Vision Experiment Here